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PUBLICISTIC GENRES IN THE FORMATION OF THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

As we know, nowadays training in the system of higher professional education in Kazakhstan requires highly qualified specialists. The formation of communicative competence of a future specialist is one of the actual problems in the process of education. This article aims to determine the possible ways of the publicistic genres in the formation of the communicative competence of future teachers. Furthermore, the article delineates the term communicative competence and its methodological aspects, discusses the classification of the publicistic genres, analyze the types of publicistic genres which can help to develop the level of communicative competence of future teachers of foreign language.

Keywords: competence, communicative competence, foreign language, future teachers of foreign languages, publicistic genres.

Introduction

Modern society is developing very dynamically. Integration of Kazakhstan into the world educational space actualizes the development of professional contacts with representatives of foreign countries and puts forward new requirements for graduates. The purpose of higher education is to train specialists with professional, communicative, and foreign language competence, creative potential, and critical thinking style. In this regard, there is a need to transform the educational environment of higher education into a single creatively developing educational space that promotes the formation of communicative competence as a factor of successful self-realization in professional activities. In a broad sense, communicative competence can be interpreted as an ability and readiness to carry out foreign language communication, both interpersonal and intercultural.

Communicative competence is one of the most important qualitative characteristics of an individual, allowing him to realize his needs for social recognition, respect, and self-actualization in the process of socialization. American linguist N. Chomsky was one of the first who introduced this term into scientific usage, by

which he understood "the system of intellectual abilities, the system of knowledge and beliefs that develops in early childhood and interaction with many other factors determines ... types of behavior". Ethnolinguist D. Hymes defined communicative competence as "the creative ability of a person to use the inventory of linguistic means (in the form of statements and discourses), which is composed of knowledge and readiness to use them adequately.

In the literature, scientists, recognizing the importance of one or another component in the professional competence of the teacher, point to the special role of the communicative component. The formation of this component is considered to be an important condition for the development of the professional activity of a teacher and his/her professional competence. Especially in foreign language teaching methodology, the development and formation of students' foreign language communicative competence are considered the main goal of foreign language teaching. The importance of communicative competence is explained not only by the fact that a foreign language is a subject of study (at university) and the subject of teaching (at school), but also by the fact that communicative prop-

erties of personality, including sociability, empathy, reflection, etc., are of great importance in pedagogical activity in general.

Language training implies both general cultural development of the student and professional development. One of the key factors in foreign language training is that graduates should not only acquire direct knowledge of a foreign language but also use it adequately in various communication situations. A. N. Shchukin and G. M. Frolova hold a similar point of view, who believe that the main purpose of foreign language training is the ability to use it for practical purposes in various situations of communication. In other words, the goal of teaching a foreign language is the formation of professional language competence, which includes understanding and generating texts on a given professional topic and the adequate use of language tools in a given situation of communication. To achieve this goal the learning process must simulate real communication.

Formation of communicative competence takes place in the process of active speech activity of students during classes. An important task of the teacher is to create real and imaginary situations of communication through games, discussions, creative projects, etc. Also, an important role is played by publicistic genres in the formation of communicative competence. Publicistic genres such as essays, public speaking, interviews, and articles help in the development of speech and writing skills of future foreign language teachers.

All of the above is closely related to the publicistic genre and this leads us to the conclusion that in forming the communicative competence of future teachers of foreign language it is necessary to use the possibilities of the publicistic genre. The purpose of this article is to identify these possibilities of the publicistic genre by conducting a questionnaire among foreign language teachers.

Literature review

General educational and upbringing tasks are subject to practical ones and are solved in the course of the implementation of the act of communicative activity at one level or another, that is, the ability to enter into intercultural communication. The entire learning process is subject to the main task - the formation of communicative competence. Communicative competence is the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to understand others and generate their own speech behavior programs that are adequate to the goals, areas, and situations of communication. On the basis of communicative competence, the process of professional activity of a foreign language teacher is realized, so we see it necessary to expand this concept.

The problem of forming communicative competence is the subject of many studies in the field of pedagogy. This has been discussed by a great number of authors in literature. Several studies suggest that in domestic linguodidactics, communicative competence is commonly understood as "a phenomenal category that reflects normative knowledge of the semantics of language units of different levels, mastery of the mechanisms for constructing and paraphrasing statements, the

ability to generate a discourse of any length, in accordance with the cultural and speech situation, including the parameters of the addressee, place, time and conditions communication, the ability to realize in foreign speech the differences between native and foreign languages, to carry out a conscious and automatic transfer of language means from one type of speech activity to another, from one situation to another.

Y.M. Zhukov considers communicative competence as "readiness and ability to plan and implement effective communicative actions using available external and internal resources". L.A. Petrovskaya pays special interest to the issue of communicative competence, defining it as "... the ability to establish and maintain necessary contacts with people..." and identifying it with competence. T.D. Kudritskaya defines it in this way "Communicative competence is a mastery of all types of speech activity in the spheres relevant to educational and cognitive, professional and cultural and cognitive activities". Volkova L.V. notes that communicative competence is a set of knowledge, abilities, skills in the field of verbal and non-verbal means for adequate perception and reflection of reality in various communication situations.

In short, the literature pertaining to researchers strongly suggests that communicative competence is "the ability to use the language being studied to carry out speech activity in accordance with the goals and situation of communication within a particular area of activity". Some authors have driven the further development of communicative competence, which it includes, according to A.N. Shchukin, specific types of competencies: 1) linguistic (or language); 2) sociolinguistic (speech); 3) sociocultural; 4) social; 5) strategic (compensatory); 6) discursive; 7) subject. The legitimacy of the allocation of such subspecies of communicative competence is explained by the complexity of the implementation of foreign language speech activity. N.D. Galskova and N.I. Gez consider the following components of communicative competence: 1) knowledge about the system of the language being studied and skills in operating language means of communication; 2) the ability to understand and generate foreign language statements, formed on the basis of linguistic knowledge and language skills, to combine them in the course of one act of communication in accordance with a specific communication situation, speech task and communicative intention; 3) knowledge of the socio-cultural specifics of the country of the language being studied, as well as skills and abilities that allow for verbal and non-verbal communication with native speakers of this language in accordance with the specifics and norms governing verbal interaction in the corresponding linguo-ethno-cultural community

The literature review shows that to date, there are many works of Kazakh scientists devoted to the problem of the formation of communicative competence. Each of the researchers gives his own interpretation of the definition and offers a component composition of communicative competence. For instance, Akeshova defines speech, information and sociocultural components, Kudritskaya describes speech, sociological, discursive, linguistic, strategic, intercultural components

of the communicative competence. Moreover, V.V. Safonova identifies the following components of foreign language communicative competence: 1) linguistic (grammatical, linguistic); 2) speech (pragmatic, strategic, discursive); 3) sociocultural (sociolinguistic, linguocultural).

All of the above is closely related to the publicistic genre, and this leads us to the conclusion that in the formation of the communicative competence of future teachers of a foreign language, it is necessary to use the possibilities of the publicistic genre. One of the main aims of this research is, also, to clarify the possibilities of the publicistic genres in the formation of communicative competence. In accordance, several studies suggest that communication is an important component of human life in modern society, its self-realization and socialization. Successful mastery of the basics of communication is an important component of the formation of a communicative personality both in interpersonal and international communication, and in the professional sphere. That is why the problem of the formation of the communicative competence and its sub-competencies of the individual is relevant today. Furthermore, future teachers of a foreign language will often have to speak in different audiences - in front of students, colleagues, etc. The ability to correctly build your speech depending on the goals and objectives of communication will allow you to assess the quality of training of future teachers. And from this it turns out that publicistic genre and communicative competence are closely connected and influence to each other. Because the publicistic genre is a speech activity in the social field in all its variety of meanings. This is the language of newspapers and magazines, radio and television programs, the language of speeches at meetings, rallies, celebrations, which is designed for an emotional impact on the listener (audience). Bakhtin divides this publicistic genre into three sub-genres:

- 1) Informational genre - combines an eventful occasion for a speech (note, interview, report).
- 2) Analytical genre - combines a deep study of life and a comprehensive analysis of facts (conversation, article, review, commentary on films or critique).
- 3) Artistic-publicistic genres include emotional expressiveness, linguistic and stylistic features. The fact is that the ability to rise above the phenomenon, above the fact is more important for the author (essay, feuilleton, pamphlet).

In our assumptions, by using these publicistic genres we can form sub-competencies or, in other words, components of communicative competence of future teachers of foreign languages. As an example let's take Safonova's description, as we have mentioned before: to form a linguistic sub-competence (grammatical, linguistic) we can use article, essay, report; to set up a speech sub-competence (pragmatic, strategic, discursive) we can assume conversation, public speaking, review; to establish a sociocultural sub-competence (sociolinguistic, linguocultural) we should use interview, critique.

Thus, it can be determined that communicative competence and its sub-competencies is a far from un-

ambiguous concept. Numerous aspects of the generation and flow of various types of speech activity are important and significant here: from the grammatical design of the statement (in accordance with the rules for the functioning of the language units of a foreign language) to the awareness of sociocultural features (in one's own speech works and statements of the speech partner), reflecting the linguistic picture of the world inherent in given foreign language. Communicative competence is formed in the process of studying a complex of professional and special academic disciplines in a foreign language, of course, and in addition, due to the complexity of the described phenomenon and the manifestation in it of such personal properties of students as purposefulness, confidence, will, attention, perseverance. Because they are necessary for acquiring systematic knowledge about the linguistic system of a foreign language, about the national and cultural features of the social and speech behavior of native speakers; for the formation of skills and abilities to participate in foreign language communication, to maintain it.

METHODS

Research Design

This study is a quantitative research design aimed at identifying widely used publicistic genres in the classroom by EFL teachers. The data was collected through a survey which conducted online by using Google Forms. The study of publicistic genres that affect the competence of students, with the help of survey items, revealed the main key feature that affects precisely the communicative competence of students.

Participants

The participants of this study were 15 schoolteachers majoring in English language teaching at the schools of Almaty in Kazakhstan. The teachers were primary (33.3%), secondary (46.7%) and high school (20%) teachers. The average age of teachers ranged from 22 to 30 years and all of them were female teachers. The number of participants remained 15 unchanged from the beginning till the end.

Instrument

The main instrument used for this study was a short questionnaire which consisted of two sections: Section 1 required participants to provide general demographic information (age, sex, etc.) as well as information about stage of school (primary, secondary, high). Section 2 contained types of publicistic genres to identify the most common genres used by EFL teachers in English lessons, as well as the types of sub-competencies that are developed when using publicistic genres.

Results

The research question of this study was aimed at clarifying the main publicistic genres that are used by teachers in teaching English. Responses to some questions were analyzed for teachers from three stages of school (primary, secondary and high). In general, the attitude of teachers to the use of the publicistic genre was positive. In particular, the sub-competencies of communicative competencies also showed positive dynamics.

Table 1.

The most common publicistic genres in the English classrooms

Genres \ Stages	Essay	Report	Interview	Conversation	Public Speaking	Article	Notes
Primary School	23.1%	7.7%	42.6%	76.9%	30.8%	0%	23.1%
Secondary School	61.5%	38.5%	38.5%	69.2%	61.5%	23.1%	30.8%
High School	75%	91.7%	75%	41.7%	58.3%	75%	41.7%

In Table 1, we can see that primary school teachers mainly use conversation (76.9%) and interviews (42.6%) during an English lessons; secondary school teachers use conversation (69.2%), essay (61.5%), and public speaking (61.5%); high school teachers often use the report (91.7%), in addition to essays (75%), articles (75%) and interviews (75%).

Research question 1. *What types of publicistic genres will increase the speaking skills of the pupils?*

Figure 1. Increasing of speaking skills by publicistic genres

As can be seen as a result, in teachers point of view, interview, conversation and public speaking will increase the colloquial speech of schoolchildren.

Research question 2. *What kind of sub-competences of communicative competence are developed during the interview?*

Figure 2. Developing of sub-competences during the

Figure 2 shows the main sub-competences that are developed during interviews in foreign language lessons. The vast majority of participants (60%) chose the sociolinguistic and discursive sub-competences, as well as sociolinguistic sub-competence helps to produce sociolinguistically appropriate utterances, discursive sub-competence assists to produce coherent and cohesive statements.

Research question 3. *What kind of sub-competence of communicative competence are more developed during the essay and article?*

Figure 3. Developing of sub-competences during the essay and article

As can be seen from Figure 3, most teachers believe that the grammatical sub-competence is one of the most developing sub-competences when writing essays and articles for schoolchildren. Because grammatical sub-competence helps to create grammatically correct utterances, what is needed for the article and essay.

Discussion

The main purpose of this study is to form communicative competence with the help of publicistic genres. According to the survey, during an English lesson, 66.7% of teachers use publicistic genres constantly, 20% of them use sometimes, 13.3% of them do not use them at all. Regarding communicative competence,

86.7% of teachers constantly work on improving communicative competence during an English lesson, 13.3% of the rest work on improving it only occasionally.

According to the results of the survey, teachers of different school stages use only certain publicistic genres for their students to form communicative competence. Why? Because each stage has its own level of cognitive thinking. If the school stage is higher, then the skills of the students is higher become correspondingly. With the help of Bloom's taxonomy, this can be easily determined (Figure 4).

Bloom's Taxonomy

Figure 4. Bloom's taxonomy

For example, primary school children can only remember and understand information. Because the first level begins with the memorization and reproduction of the received information. The student learns basic terms, basic facts, rules and can repeat them. Then comes understanding and awareness, as this is the ability to present the material in your own words. During an English lesson, it can be used a conversation and an interview from publicistic genres. On the application of other genres, they are not yet ready, because their level of cognitive thinking is still low. For the secondary school students, it is already possible to use essays and public speaking from genres, because they can already apply and analyze information. It means that the student learns to use the acquired knowledge in specific situations. He can also solve practical problems with the help of new rules and formulas, understand the structure of the material and be able to divide it into related parts. The student sees the principle of data construction and can find logical errors. For the high school, an article and a report can be used, since they already know how to evaluate and create information. In addition, he already knows how to generalize and combine his knowledge. He can evaluate statements using criteria that he can formulate himself or with the help of a teacher. It is important that he is able to evaluate the logic of the construction of the material, check the accuracy of the conclusions and argue his point of view. From this, it turns out that if publicistic genres are often used during an English lesson, then with the help of them, students of schools, also, future teachers of foreign languages:

- 1) master the technique of communication;
- 2) master speech etiquette;
- 3) master the strategy and tactics of dialogic and group communication;
- 4) learn to solve various communicative tasks;
- 5) have the opportunity to freely express their opinion;
- 6) in the process of activity to successfully implement speech communication;
- 7) can understand the facts and expressively convey the idea in writing;
- 8) master visual means, linguistic and stylistic features;
- 9) expand their horizons and form the integrity of attention with the help of newspapers;
- 10) appropriately use verbal methods in teaching.

Conclusion

Thus, foreign language communicative competence plays an important role in the training of future teachers, which can be developed through publicistic genres. Future teachers of a foreign language will often have to speak in different audiences - in front of students, colleagues, etc. The ability to correctly build the speech depending on the goals and objectives of communication will allow them to assess the quality of training of future teachers.

Actually, communicative competence is understood by us as an integrative characteristic of a specialist's personality, including knowledge, skills, abilities and personal qualities that ensure productive communication and professionalism in the field of activity. And

if it will be developed with the help of publicistic genres, then communicative competence consists of the ability to understand, reproduce and generate the meaning of the statement in accordance with the specific situation of communication and the socio-cultural context, as well as perform speech actions adequately to communicative intentions and goals, communicate taking into account the mental state and social status of interlocutors, to possess adequate speech skills, language skills and knowledge of phonetic, grammatical and lexical phenomena inherent in this language as a system.

This study has eliminated all the gaps that may arise when using publicistic genres during the educational process, and confirmed the role of the complexity of publicistic genres in the formation of communicative competence. The results obtained verified that using publicistic genres it is possible to form the communicative competence of students, as well as future teachers of foreign languages.

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